

CERTIFICATE OF ACHIVEMENT

this certificate is proudly presented to

NEW INNOVATION IN NATIONAL EDUCATION

JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Umarova Nargizaxon Rustamovna

O'ZBEK VA INGLIZ TILLARIDA METAFORALAR

LINGVOKULTUROLOGIYASI

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

zenodo

2022-NOYABR

